

Research Article

Evaluation of Noise Levels in Selected Areas in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Noise pollution is a menace worldwide, Akure, Nigeria is inclusive. The study was undertaken to evaluate the noise levels in commercial, residential, stadium, church, hospital, library, mechanic workshop, livestock, and bank areas in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The sampling was carried out two times a day (10 -11 am and 1-2 pm) for ten days using a sound level meter. The results (dBA) of the different locations in triplicate were: commercial (78.5-106.8), residential (41.3-50.5), hospital (48.8-52.0), bank (41.2-52.0), Livestock (35.4-57.8), library (44.9-61.6), mechanic workshop (71.0-101.8), stadium (74.0-106.2), and church (48.8-77.2). In comparison with international standards, it was observed that the majority of the recorded values were above the recommended limits of 55-65 (India), 45-55 (Australia), 50-60 (Japan), 50-60 (USEPA), and 35-60 (NESREA). Also, in comparison with the noise chart average decibel levels for everyday sounds, the noise levels of the study areas could be ranged as moderate (40 - 60 dBA) to extremely loud (90 - 110 dBA). To reduce the hearing problems of the individual, hearing aids should be used.

Keywords: Noise pollution, Standard limits, hearing aids, WHO, NESREA

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Introduction

Noise at an elevated decibel is pollution, it causes a disturbance. According to Mercola (2015), the problem of air pollution is associated with stress, high blood pressure, hearing loss, heart disease, sleep disturbance, and lots more. In the US, at a low noise level of 5 dB has led to the prevalence of high blood pressure and coronary heart disease. Further,

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in the submission, the economic advantage of noise pollution reduction was estimated at \$3.9 billion/ year (Mercola, 2015). When noise becomes a nuisance, it affects the performance of the activities of the surrounding areas, for example, in school settings, students, inhabitants, and teachers feel dissatisfied. It is expected that in a noisy hospital, patients and other inhabitants will be adversely disturbed. In Malaysia, continuous exposure to noise levels of 85-90 dBA has been reported to suffer from hearing (Yuen, 2014). A report released noted that over 10 million adults and 5.2 million children from the US suffered from irreversible noise-induced hearing impairment (WHO, 1991). Also, a report put it that above 250 million people worldwide are prone to the side effects of high levels of noise (Seidman and Standring, 2010). In Africa especially Nigeria noise is a great problem due to the increases in population, vehicular movements, residential and industrial activities. This problem is traceable to a number of perceived factors that are classified as i. Socio-economic and cultural factors; ii. Attitude or behavioral factors; iii. the structure of Nigerian cities (Abel, 2015). Researchers classified noise sources into internal (activities, office equipment and operation of building services) and external (sound outside the building) (Ganiyu and Ogunsote, 2010). The Nigerian government made frantic efforts to reduce the menace by promulgating Laws (Liable on conviction to the penalty specified in section 36 or 37 of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act) (FEPA, 1992).

This study was undertaken in Akure, the capital of Ondo State, which can be classified as a relatively medium-large urban city, located in the South-western part region of Nigeria. The city has a population of 421,100. The geographical coordinates are 5° 10' 0", East, 5° 14' 0" (Latitude), 7° 14' 0", 7° 18' 0" North (Longitude) at an elevation/altitude of meters, with an average elevation of 353 meters (Garg and Maji, 2016). Studies have been carried out in Akure on Buildings (Ganiyu and Ogunsote, 2010), Traffic (Fadairo, 2013), Industry (Anjorin *et al.*, 2015), but none delved into general noise sources.

The aim of the study was to determine the noise level from nine different locations (Commercial, residential, stadium, church, hospital, library, mechanic workshop, livestock, and bank). The sampling was carried out two times a day (10 -11 am and 1-2 pm) for ten days using the sound level meter.

Material and Methods

The sampling was held in Akure, the capital of Ondo State, Nigeria. Akure city is a fast-growing urban town. The sound levels were taken at nine different locations (commercial, residential, stadium, church, hospital, library, mechanic workshop,

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livestock, and bank). The sampling was carried out two times a day (10 -11 am and 1-2 pm) for ten days using the sound level meter (GB: 2266204, made in China): Measurement range 30dBA - 130dBA, accuracy ($\pm 1.5\text{dB}$), frequency range (31.5Hz - 8kHz) and power

Fig 1: The location of the noise assessment

supply (3*1.5V AAA battery). The meter was switched on, after 1sec the screen LCD panel displayed the sound level of the current environmental noise, then MIN button was pressed, a value appeared, replacing the current environmental noise when this value was stabilized, it was read as the MIN sound level of the noise source. The same procedure was applied to the MAX reading. Noise level readings (dBA) were taken directly from the noise sources. The generated values (triplicates) were statistically analyzed using Minitab 16 Statistical Software (Abulude *et al.*, 2018).

Results and Discussion

Table 2a and 2b showed the results (dBA) of the different locations to be: Commercial (78.5-106.8), residential (41.3-50.5), hospital (48.8-52.0), bank (41.2-52.0), Livestock (35.4-57.8), library (44.9-61.6), mechanic workshop (71.0-101.8), stadium (74.0-106.2), and church (48.8-77.2). From the results too in Figure 2a and 2b, the mean values of locations were: bank (45.7 dBA) and with a frequency of 2, hospital (55 dBA) with frequency of above 2, church (64.19 dBA) with frequency of 2.5 and standard deviation of 8.4, livestock (44.64 dBA) with frequency of 2.7 and standard deviation of 7.43, and stadium (88.34 dBA) with frequency of 1.8 and deviation of 11.22, commercial (94.4 dBA) with frequency of 2, library (55.34 dBA), residential (46.22 dBA), mechanic workshop (78.19 dBA). From the mean results of the different locations, it was observed that the commercial, stadium, mechanic workshop and church areas were the highest areas that produced high noise levels. The results were ranged as: commercial > stadium > mechanic workshop > church > library > hospital > residential > bank > livestock. The standard deviations were low showing that in each of the sampling sites, there were no many differences between the measurements.

Figure 2a: The frequency data of the results

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Figure 2b: The frequency data of the results

Table 1: Noise Level in this study compared with international standards (dBA)

Locations	This study	India	Australia	Japan	USEPA (2014)	NESREA (1992)
Commercial	78.5-106.8	55-65	45-55	50-60	50-60	35-60
Residential	41.3-50.5					
Hospital	48.8-52.0					
Bank	41.2-52.0					
Livestock	35.4-57.8					
Library	44.9-61.6					
Mechanic	71.0-101.8					
Workshop						
Stadium	74.0-106.2					
Church	48.8-77.2					

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Table 2: The noise chart average decibel levels for everyday sounds

Sound Effect	Decibel Levels
Painful	120 - 150 dBA
Extremely Loud	90 - 110 dBA
Very Loud	70 - 90 dBA
Moderate	40 - 60 dBA
Faint	30dBA

In comparison with international standards (Table 1), it was observed that the majority of the recorded values were above the recommended limits of 55-65 (India), 45-55 (Australia), 50-60 (Japan), 50-60 (USEPA), and 35-60 (NESREA). In comparison with the noise chart average decibel levels for everyday sounds (Table 2), the noise levels of the study areas could be ranged as moderate (40 - 60 dBA) to extremely loud (90 - 110 dBA). The study showed that the highest results were detected during the rush hours especially when school children resume for school and when the workers leave for their respective homes. The high noise pollution from the commercial area was influenced by the high traffic (vehicles and humans), that of the stadium was as a results on goalmouth scrambling, goals scored, and the vuvuzela sound used during the game, hospital high values were due to the use of vacuum cleaner during cleaning and the mower used during the cutting of grass, and in the mechanic workshop, the high results obtained were due to the panel beating of vehicles and repairs of engines. In all it would be a nice idea if the noise levels were reduced, soundproof or hearing aids used.

Conclusion

The study was undertaken to assess the noise levels in a viewing center in Akure, Nigeria. Five top teams from different continents were selected for the study. The results obtained were compared with WHO, NESREA, USEPA, and other international standards. Based on this, it was observed that most levels of noise in these locations were higher and above the standard limits. The high noise pollution from the commercial area was influenced by the high traffic (vehicles and humans), that of the stadium was as a results on goalmouth scrambling, goals scored, and the vuvuzela sound used during the game, hospital high values were due to the use of vacuum cleaner during cleaning and the mower used during the cutting of grass, and in the mechanic workshop, the high results obtained were due to the panel beating of vehicles and repairs of engines. To reduce the hearing problems of the individual, hearing aids should be used.

Figure 3: The boxplot of the sampling locations

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Conflict of interest

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

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